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Companies in the Administrative Activities and Support Services Sector in OECD Countries

The OECD calculates the number of companies operating in the administrative activities and support services sector. These are companies active in "Rental and leasing activities", "Work activities", "Travel agencies, tour operators, booking services and related activities", "Security and investigative activities; services to construction and landscaping activities; office administration, office support and other business support activities". The data refers to OECD countries in the period between 2005 and 2022.

Businesses operating in the Administrative Activities and Support Services sector in 2022. In 2022, the Administrative Activities and Support Services sector across OECD countries showed considerable variance in terms of the number of businesses operating, reflecting economic differences, demographic and structural among the various nations. Analyzing the data provided, we can observe that France leads this ranking with 294,485 companies, followed by Germany with 226,645 and Portugal with 221,168. This strong business presence in France can be attributed to a combination of business-friendly policies, a diversified economy and a robust domestic market. Germany, despite having fewer businesses than France, remains one of Europe's economic powerhouses, characterized by a well-developed service industry that supports its robust manufacturing sector. Portugal's surprising positioning in third place, with 221,168 companies, reflects a growing economy that has benefited from policies to support small and medium-sized enterprises and a growing internationalization of services. Spain and Italy follow with 206,915 and 162,462 businesses respectively, highlighting the importance of the services sector in two of Southern Europe's major economies. Both countries have faced significant economic challenges in recent years, but continue to maintain a strong presence in the services sector thanks to government initiatives aimed at stimulating entrepreneurship and support for SMEs. The Netherlands, with 112,034 enterprises, demonstrates the relevance of a favorable business environment and a highly qualified workforce, while Poland, with 101,162 enterprises, represents a case of rapid economic development post-EU accession, with increasing integration in European services markets. Turkey, with 66,822 businesses, displays an expanding service sector, although its economy faces significant challenges due to political and economic instability. Hungary and Belgium, with 64,040 and 54,716 enterprises

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respectively, represent medium-sized economies with well-developed service sectors, supported by favorable policies and strategic geographical positioning within Europe. Interestingly, countries such as Slovakia and Romania, with 51,524 and 46,665 companies respectively, are emerging as hubs for support services in Eastern Europe, thanks to competitive operating costs and growing investments in infrastructure. The Czech Republic, with 40,869 businesses, follows a similar trajectory, benefiting from its central location and a strong industrial sector. Sweden, with 39,078 businesses, and Israel, with 25,567, highlight how technologically advanced economies can maintain a robust service sector. Austria and Greece, with 25,393 and 25,333 businesses respectively, show different but effective approaches in supporting their service economies, Austria with solid economic stability and Greece recovering from a significant economic crisis. Nordic countries such as Finland, Norway and Denmark, with 24,370, 22,910 and 20,865 businesses respectively, confirm their commitment to a well-developed and sustainable service economy. Ireland, with 20,722 businesses, benefits from its position as an international hub for financial and technology services. Countries with relatively fewer businesses, such as Costa Rica (18,145), Lithuania (13,409), and Croatia (12,956), represent emerging economies that are rapidly developing their service sectors through incentive policies and investments in technology and training. Countries such as Bulgaria (11,649) and Switzerland (9,502), with economies differing in size and structure, continue to maintain a significant presence in the services sector thanks to favorable economic conditions and a qualified workforce. Slovenia and Estonia, with 9,487 and 7,671 companies respectively, reflect smaller but dynamic economies, capable of attracting investments thanks to innovation and digitalisation policies. Nations with the lowest number of businesses operating in the sector, such as Cyprus (4,529), Malta (3,421), and Luxembourg (2,218), have niche economies which, although small in terms of the number of businesses, offer highly specialized services and competitive on an international level. Finally, Bosnia and Herzegovina and North Macedonia, with 1,817 and 1,556 enterprises respectively, represent developing countries with significant growth potential in the services sector, although they face challenges related to economic stability and attracting foreign investment. In conclusion, the Administrative Activities and Support Services sector in OECD countries in 2022 displays a variety of dynamics that reflect the different economic, political and social realities of each nation. While some countries dominate the scene with a large number of companies, others emerge as new players thanks to innovative policies and strategic investments. This diversity contributes to the resilience and global competitiveness of the services sector, which remains a key pillar for modern economies.

Companies operating in the administrative activities and support services sector between 2005 and 2022. In the period between 2005 and 2022, the administrative activities and support services sector in OECD countries saw significant growth, with variations absolute and percentages that reflect the economic development and entrepreneurial support policies of each nation. Analyzing the data, it can be observed that Slovakia recorded the most impressive growth with an increase of 48,998 businesses, corresponding to an incredible increase of 1939.75%. This dramatic increase can be attributed to economic reforms, infrastructure improvements and a favorable environment for foreign investment, which have transformed Slovakia into an emerging hub for support services. Lithuania and Estonia follow with percentage increases of 403.15% and 348.07% respectively, with absolute growth of 10,744 and 5,959 companies. These Baltic countries have benefited from government policies that incentivize innovation and entrepreneurship, as well as increasing integration into European markets. Costa Rica, with an increase of 328.66% and 13,912 new businesses, reflects a similar dynamic, with policies aimed at diversifying the economy and attracting foreign investment. The Netherlands saw a notable increase of 82,028 businesses, representing an increase of 273.37%. This country has a long tradition of supporting entrepreneurial activities, with a stable economic environment and favorable regulations. Slovenia and Cyprus, with percentage increases of 260.86% and 254.94%, also

demonstrate the importance of a favorable regulatory environment and incentive policies for small and medium-sized enterprises. Romania and Ireland both recorded significant growth, with absolute increases of 33,132 and 14,649 businesses respectively, and percentage increases of 244.82% and 241.22%. These countries have benefited from economic development policies aimed at stimulating innovation and improving technological infrastructures, making them attractive for new businesses. Belgium and Latvia, with growth of 240.29% and 211.22%, saw respective increases of 38,637 and 4,782 companies. In Belgium, the central geographic location and a stable market have contributed to this growth, while Latvia has leveraged a skilled workforce and policies to support entrepreneurship. Austria and Poland recorded increases of 183.09% and 178.86% respectively, with absolute increases of 16,423 and 64,885 companies. Poland, in particular, has shown robust economic growth thanks to an increase in foreign investment and improved infrastructure. Bulgaria and Finland saw significant increases, of 157.72% and 133.23% respectively, with absolute increases of 7,129 and 13,921 businesses. These countries have implemented policies to support new businesses and improved access to financing, contributing to their growth. Germany, with an increase of 127.82% and 127,159 new businesses, reflects the stability and strength of its economy, supported by a solid service sector. Similarly, Portugal, with an increase of 126.99% and 123,733 new businesses, shows a notable economic recovery and growing government support for small and medium-sized businesses. France and Spain recorded increases of 124.70% and 94.24%, with absolute increases of 163,427 and 100,391 companies respectively. These countries, despite economic challenges, have continued to support the service sector through targeted policies and tax incentives. Luxembourg, Sweden and Denmark saw increases of 79.16%, 56.73% and 50.04% respectively, with absolute increases of 980, 14,144 and 6,959 businesses. These countries, despite having fewer businesses, maintain a highly competitive and innovative service sector. Hungary and Norway, with increases of 42.19% and 39.41%, saw absolute growth of 19,002 and 6,477 companies respectively. These countries continued to support entrepreneurship and innovation, albeit at a more moderate pace than others. Greece, with an increase of 27.77% and 5,506 new businesses, reflects a post-crisis economic recovery and growing support for SMEs. The Czech Republic recorded an increase of 10.77% with 3,973 new businesses, demonstrating stable but limited growth. Finally, Italy saw an increase of 2.60% with 4,123 new businesses, highlighting moderate growth in the services sector. This reflects a combination of economic and political challenges, but also the potential for further improvements through more targeted support policies. In summary, the period between 2005 and 2022 saw varied growth in the Administrative Activities and Support Services sector across OECD countries, with some countries experiencing notable increases thanks to effective support policies and infrastructure improvements. Others, while showing more moderate growth, continue to maintain a significant presence in the sector, highlighting the importance of a favorable economic environment for business development.

Economic policies to increase businesses operating in the administrative activities and support services sector. Economic policies aimed at increasing businesses in the administrative activities and support services sector must focus on a series of strategic interventions aimed at creating a favorable environment for the development and growth of these activities. An integrated approach that combines tax incentives, easier access to credit, training and skills development, and improved technological infrastructure can be particularly effective. First of all, tax incentives represent a fundamental lever for stimulating the creation and growth of businesses in this sector. Reducing income taxes for new businesses, as well as introducing tax credits for investments in technology and training, can significantly reduce initial operating costs and encourage innovation. Furthermore, the adoption of measures such as the deductibility of expenses for staff training and research and development can incentivize companies to invest in the continuous improvement of their skills and

operational capabilities. At the same time, facilitated access to credit is crucial to allow companies to finance their activities and expansion projects. In this context, the creation of public guarantee funds can reduce the risk for financial institutions and increase the availability of loans on favorable terms. Even the introduction of innovative financial instruments, such as minibonds or participatory financing, can offer valid alternatives for raising capital, especially for small and medium-sized businesses that often encounter difficulties in accessing traditional financial markets. Training and skills development constitute another fundamental pillar for the growth of the sector. Continuous training programs, professional refresher courses and certification paths can increase the quality of the service offered by companies and make them more competitive. In this context, collaboration between educational institutions, public and private bodies is essential to ensure that training programs effectively respond to the needs of the labor market. Furthermore, the adoption of active labor policies, such as incentives for hiring young and unemployed people, can help create a constant flow of new talent within the sector. The improvement of technological infrastructures represents a further key element to support companies in the sector of administrative activities and support services. Investments in high-speed communications networks, digital platforms and advanced management tools can increase operational efficiency and allow businesses to offer more sophisticated and higher-quality services. Promoting the adoption of emerging technologies, such as artificial intelligence and process automation, can also open up new business opportunities and make companies more resilient and able to quickly adapt to market changes. Finally, it is critical to foster a stable and predictable regulatory environment that fosters business growth. The simplification of bureaucratic procedures, the reduction of times and costs of starting and managing activities, and the protection of intellectual property rights are elements that can contribute to creating a favorable context for the development of the sector. The transparency and efficiency of public administration are equally crucial to building the trust of entrepreneurs and attracting investments. In summary, a coherent set of economic policies that embraces tax incentives, access to credit, training and skills development, improved technological infrastructure and a favorable regulatory environment can create the ideal conditions for increasing businesses operating in the administrative and support services, thus contributing to overall economic well-being.

Conclusions. The number of companies operating in the administrative activities and support services sector grew in OECD countries by an average of 105.24% between 2005 and 2022. The countries in which these values grew the most between 2005 and 2022 are the Slovak Republic with +1939.75, Lithuania with 403.15% and Estonia with +348.07%. The countries in which these values have grown the least are Greece with +27.77%, the Czech Republic with +10.77%, and Italy with 2.60%. If the number of companies operating in this sector in Italy had been in line with the OECD average, in 2022 Italy would have been the leading country in terms of number of companies in the administrative activities and support services sector. However, low growth has caused Italy to slip to fifth place, overtaken by Spain, Portugal, Germany and France.

Declarations

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Number of Enterprises in Administrative and Support Service Activities (2022)

Percentage Change in Number of Enterprises in Administrative and Support Service Activities (2005-2022)